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ANALYSIS OF VIBRATIONS OF THE ELASTIC PLATE OF THE
NETWORK SURFACE OF THE CLEANER UNDER RANDOM
DISTURBANCE FROM RAW COTTON

Shavkat Behbudov., Nazimjon Komilov

Bukhara Engineering and Technological Institute

Известно, что при первичной обработке хлопка-сырца усовершенствование технологических оборудование является актуальной проблемы является хлопка- очистительных предприятие. В статье излагается решение эти проблемы.

Ключевые слова и выражения:упругой пластины, сетчатый поверхность, мелкий сор, оборудование, колосниковой решетки, барабан, колок, возбуждающий сила, амплитуда, колебание.

The Known that under primary processing the pat-product in its raw state improvement technological equipment is an actual problem is a pat- cleansing enterprise. Decision of this problem is stated in article.

The Keywords and expressions: springy plate, netlike surface, small litter, equipment, колосниковой of the lattice, drum, peg, agitating power, amplitude, fluctuation.

The recommended design of the mesh surface with activating elastic plates [1] allows additional shaking of cotton and intensification of the release of weed impurities, mostly small sizes. To ensure the necessary cleaning effect, it is advisable to justify the geometric and stiffness parameters of the elastic plate of the mesh surface. The calculation scheme of the elastic plate is attached to Fig.1.

where a - is the scheme of the elastic plate; b - single-mass oscillatory system; m_n is the mass of the elastic plate; c, v - are the stiffness and dissipation coefficients of the elastic plate.

Fig.1. Calculation scheme of the elastic plate of the mesh surface of the cotton purifier. According to the design scheme, a random perturbing force acts on a single-mass oscillatory system. The differential equation describing the oscillations of an elastic plate with a random perturbation, taking into account the elastic-dissipative properties of the plate, according to the methodology applied in [2,3] for a single-mass oscillatory system, has the form.

$$m_n \ddot{y} + b \dot{y} + cy = M(Q) \pm \delta Q \quad (1)$$

where, m_n - elastic plate mass; b, c - coefficients of dissipation and stiffness of the elastic plate; y - plate end movement; $M(Q)$ - mathematical expectation of the perturbing force from raw cotton ; δQ - random component of the perturbing force.

Technological resistance (disturbance) from raw cotton during its cleaning has a random character, which was determined experimentally [4]. The obtained experimental data were processed by the method of mathematical statistics, the mathematical expectation and parameters of the random component were determined. The numerical solution of the differential equation by analytical methods poses a certain difficulty. The problem was solved by a numerical method

on a PEBM using standard programs with the following calculated values of the parameters: $m_n = 3,1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg; $M(Q) = 1,2$ N; $c = 1,4 \cdot 10^3$ N/m; $b = 12,5$ Ns/m; $\delta Q = (20 \div 25)$ % from $M(Q)$.

When determining the nature of oscillations of the elastic plate of the mesh surface of the cotton purifier, an algorithm for implementation on a PEBM was compiled, which includes taking into account the random components of the perturbing force of the cotton in the form of a random number generator.

Figure 2 shows the regularities of oscillations of the elastic plate of the mesh surface of the cleaner under random exposure to raw cotton. With an average value of cotton perturbation of 1.2 N, the average value of the displacement of the elastic plate reaches $1,82 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m, the amplitude of the plate oscillations is up to $(0,42 - 0,85) \cdot 10^{-3}$ m.

In this case, the velocity range of the elastic plate reaches 1,61-2,15 m/s (see Fig. 2.a). An increase in the load from cotton significantly increases the amplitude of the elastic plate oscillation (see Fig. 2.b). With a disturbing force 1,5 H and a random component 0,14-0,16 H, the average value of the displacement of the plate reaches $2,83 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. In this case, the range of the speed of the oscillatory movement of the plate reaches 2,45- 2,82 m/s. On the basis of the results obtained, graphical dependences of the change in the range of displacement oscillations and the speed of the elastic plate of the mesh surface of the cleaner on the increase in the cotton disturbance were plotted (see Fig. 3a).

So, under load 1,2 H and plate mass $3,1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg, $\Delta y = 1,05 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m, and under load 2,5 N, it increases to $3,88 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m. In this case, the range of speed of the elastic plate increases from 0,87 m/s to 2,15 m/s. It is known that an increase in the mass of an oscillatory system leads to a decrease in the amplitude of oscillations.

For our case, at $m_n = 4,3 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg, the range of movement will change in the range of $0,67 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m to $2,08 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m, and the range of speed $\Delta y = 0,44 - 1,76$ m/s with an increase in the average load from 1,2 N to 2,5 N. According to the experimental data, the range of oscillations of the elastic plate within $(2,96 - 3,12) \cdot 10^{-3}$ m provides the

necessary cleaning efficiency of cotton. Therefore, to ensure Δy values within the specified limits, the most acceptable values of the plate mass $(0,34-0,37) \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg.

where, a - at $M(Q)=1.2 \cdot H; =(0.12-0.13) M(Q)$; b- at $M(Q)=1.5 \cdot H; =(0.12-0.13) M(Q)$; v- at $C=1.4 \cdot 10^3 \cdot H/m$; d- at $C=2.5 \cdot 10^3 \cdot H/m$;

Fig.2. Patterns of change in displacement and speed of an elastic plate of a mesh surface

where, 1,2 -; 1.3 - at $m=3.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg;

3.4 - ;2.4 - at $m=4.3 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg;

Fig.3a Graphical dependences of the change in the range of displacement oscillations and the speed of the elastic plate on the increase in the load of raw cotton

where, 1,2 -; 1.3 - at $M(Q)=1.5 \cdot H$;

3.4 -; 2.4 - at $M(Q)=1.2 \text{ N}$.

Fig.3b Graphical dependences of the change in the range of displacement oscillations and speed from the increase in the stiffness coefficient

On fig. Figure 3b shows the curves characterizing the vibrations of the plate with variations in its stiffness coefficient. With an increase in the rigidity of the elastic plate, the amplitude of oscillations of the plate displacements decreases.

From fig. 3b it can be seen that the decrease in the range of displacement and velocity oscillations with increasing stiffness coefficient values $\Delta y, \Delta \dot{y}$ is non-linear. It should be noted that the nature of the dependencies when varying the stiffness coefficient is significantly affected by the value of the load from raw cotton. So, at the value of the stiffness coefficient of the elastic plate $0.5 \cdot 10^3 \text{ N/m}$ at load 1,5 N, the range of oscillations is $\Delta y = 4,15 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$, and $\Delta \dot{y} = 2,14 \text{ m/s}$. At the value of the

stiffness coefficient $2,25 \cdot 10^3 \text{ N/m}$, the values of $\Delta y = 1,28 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$ and $\Delta \dot{y} = 0,71 \text{ m/s}$ under load 1,2 N. (see Fig. 3b, curves 1-4). Deviations of the obtained parameter values due to the influence of the random component of the load do not exceed 8,0 – 10,0%. To provide the necessary values of the amplitude of oscillations of the elastic plate $(1,48 - 1,56) \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$, the recommended values of the stiffness coefficient of the elastic plate are $(1,5 - 2,0) \cdot 10^3 \text{ N/m}$.

The most important is the study of vibrations of the elastic plate of the mesh surface of the cotton cleaner when using materials with different dissipative properties. It is known that an increase in the dissipation coefficient leads to a rapid damping of plate oscillations, especially their own [2]. With an increase in the dissipation coefficient from 12,5 Ns/m to 18,5Ns/m, the amplitude of displacement oscillations decreases on average from $1,13 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$ to $0,64 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$, and the amplitude of plate velocity oscillations decreases from 1,8 m/s to 0,98 m/s. Acceptable values of the dissipation coefficient of the elastic plate are 10,0 – 13 Ns/m.

At the same time, natural oscillations are preserved to some extent, allowing an increase in the shaking of the cotton fly, thereby increasing the cleaning effect.

Conclusions: The laws of oscillations of the elastic plate of the mesh surface of the fine litter cleaner under random perturbation from raw cotton are obtained. Graphical nonlinear dependences of the change in the range of displacement oscillations and the velocities of the elastic plate on the increase in the random perturbing force of the cotton, the coefficients of rigidity and dissipation with the variation of the mass of the elastic plate of the mesh surface of the cotton cleaner are obtained. Recommended parameter values for random perturbation from cotton: $c = (1,5 - 2,0) \cdot 10^3 \text{ N/m}$; $m_n = (0,34 - 0,37) \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ kg}$; $v = 10,0 - 13,0 \text{ Ns/m}$.

Literature

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